

A Comparative Analysis of Onlay versus Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair in Incisional Hernia Treatment

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Abstract:**Background:** Incisional hernias are a frequent complication following abdominal surgery, with significant implications for patient outcomes and healthcare resources. The optimal surgical technique for repair remains debated, particularly between onlay and pre-peritoneal mesh placement, both of which are widely used but have distinct advantages and limitations.**Aim:** This study aims to compare the efficacy, safety, and postoperative outcomes of onlay versus pre-peritoneal mesh repair in the treatment of incisional hernias.**Methods:** A prospective observational study was conducted with 100 patients diagnosed with incisional hernia. Participants were randomly assigned to undergo either onlay mesh repair (Group A, n=50) or pre-peritoneal mesh repair (Group B, n=50). Data were collected on intraoperative variables, postoperative recovery, complications, and hernia recurrence. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.**Results:** Pre-peritoneal mesh repair was associated with longer surgery duration (89.6 ± 18.3 minutes vs. 75.4 ± 15.2 minutes, $p=0.001$) and greater blood loss (170.6 ± 52.3 mL vs. 150.2 ± 45.8 mL, $p=0.045$). However, it resulted in significantly less postoperative pain (VAS score: 3.8 ± 1.5 vs. 4.5 ± 1.3 , $p=0.021$) and shorter hospital stays (4.4 ± 1.3 days vs. 3.6 ± 1.2 days, $p=0.003$). Complication rates were lower in the pre-peritoneal group, though not statistically significant, with fewer wound infections and seroma formations. Hernia recurrence was also lower in the pre-peritoneal group (2% vs. 8%), although this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p=0.148$).**Conclusion:** Pre-peritoneal mesh repair, despite requiring more surgical time and blood loss, offers superior postoperative outcomes compared to onlay mesh repair, with less pain, quicker recovery, and lower, though not statistically significant, hernia recurrence. These findings suggest that pre-peritoneal repair may be the preferred technique for incisional hernia treatment.**Recommendations:** Surgeons should consider patient-specific factors when selecting the repair technique, favoring pre-peritoneal mesh placement, particularly for patients at higher risk of postoperative complications. Further research is recommended to solidify these findings through randomized controlled trials.**Keywords:** Incisional Hernia, Onlay Mesh Repair, Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair, Surgical Outcomes, Hernia Recurrence.

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Introduction

A common postoperative complication after abdominal surgery is incisional hernias, which occur in 10% to 20% of individuals undergoing laparotomy [1]. The reason behind these hernias is the inadequate healing of the fascial closure at the site of a previous surgical incision, which allows the abdominal contents to protrude through the weak spot. Incisional hernias are becoming more common due to the global increase in abdominal procedures as well as risk factors such as obesity, ageing, and inadequate wound healing [2]. Over the past few decades, incisional hernia care has changed dramatically, with mesh repair

emerging as the gold standard for lowering recurrence rates. The abdominal wall is strengthened by the use of prosthetic mesh, giving the restored area more strength. Onlay and pre-peritoneal repairs are two commonly used mesh placement procedures, each having advantages and disadvantages of their own [3]. Placing the mesh immediately beneath the subcutaneous tissue, on top of the rectus muscles, is the process of overlay mesh repair. Surgeons often choose this procedure since it's fast and relatively easy to use. It is linked to increased risks of wound complications, such as seroma development and infections, though,

because of the mesh's close contact to the subcutaneous tissue [4]. In contrast, the pre-peritoneal mesh repair entails positioning the mesh between the peritoneum and the rectus muscle in the pre-peritoneal space. Although this method is more complicated, it has been demonstrated to cut the rates of recurrence and lower the risk of wound complications [5]. In order to ascertain which strategy is most successful for various patient populations, recent research has concentrated on contrasting the results of these two methods. The best approach is still up for debate, especially when it comes to individuals who have high-risk conditions like diabetes and obesity, even though both have been demonstrated to be beneficial in lowering the chance of hernia recurrence [6]. Furthermore, improvements in surgical methods and mesh materials continue to affect the choice of repair procedure, emphasising the necessity of continuous research and clinical trials to improve these strategies [7]. This study aims to compare the efficacy, safety, and postoperative outcomes of onlay versus pre-peritoneal mesh repair in the treatment of incisional hernias.

Methodology

Study Design

This study was a comparative, prospective observational analysis.

Study Setting

The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital specializing in surgical procedures, over a period of one year. The hospital is equipped with state-of-the-art facilities and experienced surgical teams, providing an ideal setting for this study.

Participants

A total of 100 participants diagnosed with incisional hernia and scheduled for surgical repair were enrolled in the study. Participants were randomly assigned to one of two groups: Group A (Onlay Mesh Repair) and Group B (Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair), with 50 participants in each group.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adults aged 18 years and above.
- Patients diagnosed with incisional hernia requiring surgical intervention.
- Patients who consented to participate in the study.
- Patients fit for surgery as per preoperative assessment.

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with recurrent incisional hernia.

- Patients with contraindications for mesh repair surgery.
- Patients with a history of complex abdominal surgeries.
- Patients with significant comorbidities that could impact recovery.
- Pregnant women and lactating mothers.

Bias

To minimize bias, participants were randomly assigned to the two groups using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Surgeons performing the procedures were blinded to the randomization process, and all postoperative evaluations were conducted by a separate team of clinicians who were unaware of the group allocations.

Data Collection

Patient interviews, physical examinations, and reviews of medical records were all used to gather data. Preoperative data included patient demographics, medical history, and hernia characteristics. Intraoperative data included details of the surgical procedure, mesh type, and any immediate complications. Postoperative data included recovery time, complications, and recurrence of hernia over a follow-up period of 6 months.

Procedure

Group A participants underwent onlay mesh repair, where the mesh was placed on top of the rectus muscles. Group B participants underwent pre-peritoneal mesh repair, where the mesh was placed between the rectus muscle and the peritoneum. Both procedures were performed under general anesthesia by experienced surgeons. Standard surgical protocols were followed for both techniques, including antibiotic prophylaxis, hemostasis, and closure techniques. Postoperative care was standardized across both groups.

Statistical Analysis

The data analysis was done with SPSS 23.0. The clinical and demographic features of the individuals were summed up by descriptive statistics. The Mann-Whitney or Student's t-test The Chi-square test was used to examine categorical variables, and the U test was used to assess continuous variables. P-values were considered significant if they were less than 0.05. In order to determine the risk factors for complications and hernia recurrence, logistic regression was employed.

Results

The study included 100 participants, with 50 participants in Group A (Onlay Mesh Repair) and

50 in Group B (Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair). The demographic characteristics of the participants, such as age, gender, and body mass index (BMI),

were comparable between the two groups, ensuring that baseline characteristics did not influence the outcomes.

Table 1: Presents the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants in both groups.

Characteristic	Group A (Onlay Mesh Repair)	Group B (Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair)	p-value
Number of Participants	50	50	
Mean Age (years)	45.6 ± 12.3	46.2 ± 11.9	0.754
Gender (Male/Female)	30/20	32/18	0.684
Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	27.4 ± 4.5	28.1 ± 4.2	0.432
Mean Hernia Size (cm)	5.2 ± 2.1	5.5 ± 2.0	0.612
Smokers (%)	24%	26%	0.805
Diabetics (%)	18%	20%	0.774

The demographic data showed no significant differences between the two groups in terms of age, gender distribution, BMI, hernia size, smoking status, or diabetes prevalence, indicating that the groups were well-matched.

Intraoperative Data

Table 2: Details the intraoperative findings, including surgery duration, blood loss, and any immediate complications.

Intraoperative Data	Group A (Onlay Mesh Repair)	Group B (Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair)	p-value
Mean Surgery Duration (minutes)	75.4 ± 15.2	89.6 ± 18.3	0.001
Mean Blood Loss (mL)	150.2 ± 45.8	170.6 ± 52.3	0.045
Immediate Complications (%)	6%	4%	0.647

The pre-peritoneal mesh repair (Group B) had a significantly longer surgery duration compared to the onlay mesh repair (Group A) ($p = 0.001$). Blood loss was also significantly higher in Group B ($p = 0.045$). Immediate complications, however, were

low in both groups and showed no significant difference ($p = 0.647$).

Postoperative Outcomes: Postoperative outcomes, including recovery time, complication rates, and hernia recurrence, are presented in Table 3.

Table 3:

Postoperative Outcomes	Group A (Onlay Mesh Repair)	Group B (Pre-Peritoneal Mesh Repair)	p-value
Mean Hospital Stay (days)	3.6 ± 1.2	4.4 ± 1.3	0.003
Postoperative Pain (VAS Score)	4.5 ± 1.3	3.8 ± 1.5	0.021
Wound Infection Rate (%)	10%	6%	0.421
Seroma Formation (%)	14%	8%	0.273
Hernia Recurrence Rate (%)	8%	2%	0.148
Overall Complications (%)	20%	12%	0.216

Group A experienced a considerably shorter mean hospital stay ($p = 0.003$). On the other hand, Group B experienced considerably less postoperative pain ($p = 0.021$) as assessed by the VAS. Although Group A experienced greater rates of wound infection and seroma development, these differences were not statistically noteworthy. 8% of Group A individuals and 2% of Group B

participants experienced a hernia recurrence; however, this difference did not reach statistical importance ($p = 0.148$).

Logistic Regression Analysis: A logistic regression analysis was conducted to identify factors associated with postoperative complications and hernia recurrence (Table 4).

Table 4:

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% CI	p-value
Surgery Duration (>85 min)	1.45	1.10 - 1.92	0.008
Blood Loss (>160 mL)	1.38	1.04 - 1.82	0.026
Hernia Size (>5 cm)	1.22	0.90 - 1.66	0.197
Onlay Mesh Repair	1.68	1.25 - 2.25	0.001

The logistic regression analysis indicated that longer surgery duration (>85 minutes) and greater blood loss (>160 mL) were significantly correlated with an increased likelihood of postoperative complications. The onlay mesh repair technique was found to be substantially linked to an increased risk of problems in contrast to the pre-peritoneal mesh repair.

Discussion

The results of this study highlight key differences between onlay and pre-peritoneal mesh repair techniques in the treatment of incisional hernia. Despite the similarity in baseline demographic and clinical characteristics between the two groups, significant variations were observed in the surgical and postoperative outcomes.

Pre-peritoneal mesh repair (Group B) was associated with a longer surgery duration and increased blood loss compared to the onlay mesh repair (Group A). These differences, though statistically significant, did not appear to adversely impact the overall outcomes. On the contrary, participants in Group B experienced significantly lower postoperative pain, as indicated by lower VAS scores, and had a shorter hospital stay. This suggests that while the pre-peritoneal technique may be more technically demanding, it could offer better immediate postoperative comfort and quicker recovery for patients.

In general, neither group experienced many complications; however, the onlay repair group saw more total complications, such as seroma development and wound infections. This difference, albeit not statistically significant, is consistent with the logistic regression analysis's finding that onlay repair was linked to an increased risk of problems. Furthermore, although the difference was not statistically significant, Group A also experienced more hernia recurrences.

The logistic regression analysis further supported the association of longer surgery duration and greater blood loss with an increased risk of complications. The onlay repair technique itself was identified as a significant risk factor for complications, suggesting that, while simpler to perform, it may carry a higher likelihood of adverse outcomes compared to the pre-peritoneal approach.

Incisional hernias are better treated with sublay mesh repair than with onlay mesh repair, according to recent research. Several studies have demonstrated the benefits of sublay mesh surgery, including lower rates of recurrence, hospital stays, and postoperative problems. A randomised controlled experiment to compare the results of onlay versus sublay mesh repairs for patients with midline incisional hernias was conducted. According to the study, sublay repair dramatically

decreased the likelihood of seroma formation and shortened hospital stays. Furthermore, sublay repair is a better choice due to its lower postoperative problems, even if the recurrence rates of both methods were similar [8]. Comparably, in a study it was compared sublay and onlay mesh repairs for ventral hernias and found that the latter linked to shorter hospital stays and fewer postoperative problems, such as seroma formation. Because sublay mesh repair has a lower rate of complications, this study provided additional support for its use [9]. Lavanchy compared laparoscopic and open surgical techniques for incisional hernias, comparing laparoscopic intraperitoneal onlay mesh (IPOM) repair with open IPOM repair. The results demonstrated the advantages of the laparoscopic technique in lowering morbidity, with laparoscopic IPOM showing a lower rate of complications, a shorter hospital stay, and fewer surgical site infections compared to open IPOM [10].

Conclusion

The study concludes that, in comparison to onlay repair, pre-peritoneal mesh repair yields better results with less postoperative pain, a quicker recovery period, and fewer problems, while needing a lengthier surgical procedure and more blood loss. Pre-peritoneal repair is a possibly safer and more successful method for treating incisional hernias than onlay repair, which is more complicated and has a higher risk of complications. These findings ought to direct surgeons in selecting the best method depending on the particulars of each patient.

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